

**Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability
of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through
Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge
Solutions' Gains**

D4.7: XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool (1st version)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AJAX	Asynchronous JavaScript and XML
API	Application Programming Interface
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
FR	Function Requirement
GA	Grant Agreement
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
ISP	Internet Service Provider
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KFT	Knowledge Facilitation Tool
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MVC	Model-View-Controller
NPV	Net Present Value
OPEX	Operating Expenditure
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable D4.7 - XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool (1st version) is part of Work Package 4 - XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool Development and addresses Task 4.4 - Digitalisation and Integration of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool. It is the first version of two deliverables outputted from this task, the latter, D4.8 - XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool (2nd version), to be released in M35. This deliverable D4.7 is the first version of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT), a web-based application developed in the XGain project to facilitate business model development, and support decision-making in the selection of an ecosystem of technologies, comprising of connectivity options and edge processing solutions.

In this deliverable, the configuration of the KFT is presented as defined from the KFT architecture design and technical specifications work performed in T2.4, and based on the functional and non-functional requirements specified in WP2. The front-end graphical Human Machine Interface (HMI) was developed following the Graphical User Interface (GUI) design principles, and equipped with the necessary functionalities and features to ensure implementation of the defined functional and non-functional requirements. The HMI architecture design, programming languages and tools used for the implementation are presented. Furthermore, the deliverable explains the different modules (models and databases) constituting the back-end of the KFT, including the Technology Mix finder and Dimensioning Solver models, the Techno-economic and Socio-environmental assessment models, and the Business Model proposer, and their integration and communication. The roadmap from initial mock-up designs to the KFT development and implementation is discussed, and the flow of pages and key functionalities of this first version are demonstrated using an exemplary user session. The KFT functionalities and features, graphical designs, and back-end models will be further developed and fine-tuned during the Use Case (UC) testing and validation work in WP5, before the second version of the tool, D4.8, is released.

2 Introduction

The XGain KFT seeks to address the complex challenges associated with increasing systemic resilience, improving energy efficiency, contributing to climate mitigation, and reducing digital divides across various sectors and regions. The tool is designed to offer a user-friendly HMI that ensures intuitive accessibility for non-expert personnel, and captures end-users' requirements and technical specifications, thereby enabling the development of a detailed solution – business model and technology mixture proposals, tailored to their needs. The end-user experience is central to the development of the KFT, and the HMI plays a pivotal role in ensuring its intuitiveness. End-users, ranging from municipalities and policymakers to farmers and foresters will have the capability to interact with the tool seamlessly. The HMI allows users to select specific sectors or multisectoral assessments, input location-specific needs and service demand volumes, and identify the assessment level—whether at the Regional, Community, or Farm level.

The back-end of the KFT consists of the Technology Mix finder and Dimensioning solver models developed in WP3 working in alignment with the Techno-economic and Socio-environmental assessment models produced in WP4, to support decision-making in the selection of an ecosystem of technologies, including connectivity options and processing solutions, coherently assessing their socio-economic and techno-environmental effects. In parallel, the Business model proposer facilitates business model development. These XGain system components are identified and the communication and flow of information between them is specified and described. The KFT is tested to ensure interoperability and adequate performance, prior to the UC deployment and validation.

2.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map XGain Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			

D4.7 XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool (1st version)

Initial version of the tool

TASKS			
Task 4.4 - Digitalisation and Integration of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool	Task 4.4 will perform the integration and configuration of the knowledge facilitation tool, as defined in the tool architecture of T2.4 and with respect to the system requirements determined during the T2.1 through benchmarking and compliance matrix relevant iterations.	Section 3.1 & Section 3.2	The KFT design is explained & the implementation phases and activities are presented

<p>An iterative integration methodology will be adopted, with aim to ensure collaborative technical integration work, putting together the XGain system components in a loosely coupled way towards ensuring interoperability, adequate performance and scalability for large-scale use during the project and beyond.</p> <p>Additionally, this task will design and implement the graphical HMI, by leveraging eBOS bespoke WiseBOS Platform, which is specialised for the development of such dashboards.</p> <p>The XGain tool will be developed as a stand-alone module in a lab environment to ensure its proper dry-run operation, concept verification and usability testing prior to the use case deployment and throughout the project duration, it will constantly be updated in order to integrate the feedback received from the users' experience.</p>	<p>Section 3.3 & Section 3.5</p> <p>Section 3.4</p> <p>Section 4.1 & Section 4.2</p>	<p>The KFT structure including front-end and back-end, and system components integration is discussed.</p> <p>The design principles and technologies used for the HMI development are discussed.</p> <p>The KFT development process is presented and discussed</p>
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Relations with other tasks and deliverables:

This section presents the interdependencies between this deliverable D4.7, outputted from T4.4, and other deliverables, tasks and Work Packages (WPs). These relationships are important to understand the overall XGain project workflow and connection between different parts of the work. The main inputs to this deliverable originate from T2.1 for stakeholder requirements translated to functional and non-functional requirements (D2.1), T2.4 for the analysis of requirements and the KFT architecture and technical specifications, and tasks T3.1, T3.2 (work reported in D3.1), T4.1 (in D4.1), T4.2 (in D4.3), and T4.3 (in D4.5) which present the work on the back-end models of the KFT, that have shaped the structure of the KFT front-end, including the flow of pages and the user inputs and outputs shown on the HMI.

The output of T4.4 (this deliverable report and the actual KFT web-based tool) will be used in the WP5 validation work in the 6 real-life UCs, to ensure that the KFT performs seamlessly and effectively while enhancing knowledge sharing, promoting technological solutions, and driving sustainable business models. The validation feedback will be used to fine-tune the back-end models (T3.1, T3.2, T4.1-T4.3), as well as the HMI (T4.4), to produce the second version of the KFT, outputted as D4.8, in month 35.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In this section, a description of deliverable D4.7 structure is provided, outlining the respective chapters and their content.

Chapter 1 – Executive Summary

Chapter 2 – Introduction: General information on the work and objectives of deliverable, mapping of XGain outputs in deliverable and interdependencies with other work in XGain.

Chapter 3 – Implementation approach of the KFT, outlining the implementation phases and tasks, a description of the KFT design and structure including the front-end HMI, and back-end models and their integration and communication channels; the design principles and tools used for the development of the KFT.

Chapter 4 – KFT development work flow, from initial mock-up designs to KFT implementation stage, demonstrating the functionalities and capabilities of the KFT version 1 using an exemplary session.

Chapter 5 – Conclusion and roadmap to next version.

3 Implementation Approach

It was agreed that the XGain KFT will be hosted on eBOS’s servers. This will provide an open-source version of the KFT to align with what is required by the GA and it is also the general approach favoured by the European Commission and the XGain consortium. Furthermore, to encourage a transparent and open-source culture, a free open-source version of the XGain KFT will be released, which will increase visibility, advertise the XGain solutions and make XGain brand recognisable. XGain will make accessible its software repositories through well-known distributed source code platforms such as GitHub and Bitbucket. Promoting open-source code in open repositories, XGain aims to provide added value to the European research community. This will give the opportunity for technical discussions within the research community and may result in potential change suggestions for the KFT made during those technical discussions.

This chapter provides detailed information about the design principles and methodology for the KFT design, including planning of the necessary activities, a mapping with the requirements collected in WP2 during the UC workshops and from other stakeholders, technologies used, and general features supported by the KFT.

3.1 Task Planning and Activities

This section presents the planning activities in Task T4.4 which are related to the implementation of the KFT, including obtaining the requirements and KFT architecture from WP2, and the back-end logic modules from WP3 and WP4.

The methodology followed from the functional requirements captured in WP2, to translating them to technical specifications, and utilizing them during the development of the low-level design of the KFT, is described. Based on the implementation plan, a four-phase implementation process has been followed, having in mind the requirements-design-continuum development approach. This is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Implementation phases and activities

	Activities	Partners Involved
Phase 1: Requirements collection, Architecture definition & Technology to be used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User stories and stakeholder requirements were collected in WP2 T2.1, during the UC stakeholder workshops. UC requirements were also collected. These were translated to functional and non-functional requirements for the KFT. A MOSCOW analysis was performed to set the implementation priority of the requirements (T2.4). The architecture of the KFT and technical specifications were constructed in T2.4, taking into consideration the requirements and the intended functionalities and features of the KFT. The communication between different KFT modules (front-end graphical HMI, models and databases) were defined. 	ZSI, i2CAT
Phase 2: Back-end models development & HMI “inputs” and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The KFT back-end models were developed in WP3 (Technology mix finder & Dimensioning solver) and WP4 (Techno-economic 	ICCS, INC, UW, RAIN, eBOS

<p>“outputs” definition in relation to back-end modules</p>	<p>assessment, Socio-environmental assessment, Business model proposer).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The “inputs” required by the user to provide on the user interface (UI) were defined, based on the required input parameters to the models in the back-end. The “outputs” from the models were specified, to understand what the user is provided with in the output pages of the KFT. 	
<p>Phase 3: Wireframes and Mock-up designs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KFT mock-ups were prepared using Figma wireframing tool. [1] These demonstrate the basic page structure of the KFT and main KFT features and functionalities. • The profile of target audiences was taken into consideration in this activity, to ensure a user-friendly interface, and achieve optimal “User experience”. • The information displayed on each page of the KFT (inputs and outputs) and flow of pages was discussed with the KFT implementation team to ensure compliance with the functional and non-functional requirements, and alignment with the back-end modules. • The KFT mock-up was a living element that has undergone constant updates to reflect the design decisions taken by the consortium. Several iterations of KFT mock-up led to the final mock-up design to be used in the development and implementation stage. 	<p>eBOS</p>
<p>Phase 4: Development and Implementation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of the KFT based on the approved design: Design of the front-end graphical HMI & Integration of back-end modules. • KFT functionalities and technical performance tested in lab trials on the matter of usability, user interface, the integration. • Customisation to the KFT will be made during the field trials to allow maximisation of Quality of Service (QoS) and Quality of Experience (QoE). During the field trials, feedback will be collected and be fed to WP3 and WP4 for fine-tuning of the models and optimization of the HMI. 	<p>eBOS</p>

3.2 KFT Design

3.2.1 Purpose of the KFT

The KFT serves a multifaceted purpose aimed at addressing the project's overarching objectives. Its core purpose is to facilitate business model development, support decision-making processes, and aid in the selection of an ecosystem of technologies, encompassing connectivity options and edge processing solutions. Operating under

a multi-actor and practitioner-oriented approach, the KFT takes into account socio-economic and techno-environmental factors. Its primary goals include increasing systemic resilience, improving energy efficiency, contributing to climate mitigation, and reducing digital divides across diverse sectors and regions.

The KFT design should provide a user-centric, interoperable, and easy-to-use tool, catering to actors in rural and coastal communities. Its functionality extends to the development, selection, and implementation of innovative business models, with a focus on last-mile connectivity solutions and edge processing alternatives. The tool should assess connectivity and edge processing solutions at multiple levels – farm, community, and regional, and across several sectors, including agriculture, forestry and eHealth, and other services.

3.2.2 Mapping with Functional/Non-Functional Requirements

In WP2 the requirements for the KFT were collected from three main sources: the project scope and objective analysis, from stakeholder analysis, and from partners' expertise. In T2.4, the requirements were consolidated and prioritized to allow for the design choices of the architecture. The functional and non-functional requirements were classified into three main categories: (a) HMI related, (b) Tools and methods related, and (c) a combination of HMI and tool-related. These were then assigned an implementation priority using the MoSCoW method, and were characterised as "Must-", "Should-", "Could-", or "Will-not-" have requirements. The requirements considered in the HMI design were mainly the "HMI related" and "Combination of HMI and tool-related" requirements, whereas the "Tools and methods related" requirements were accounted for in T4.1, T4.2, T4.3 and WP3, for the techno-economic, socio-environmental, business models, and technology-mix finder and dimensioning solver models, which constitute the back-end of the KFT.

Table 3 below presents the requirements that concern the HMI design of the 1st KFT version, and are satisfying requirements that were mostly classified as "Must" or "Should" have. Lower priority requirements will be considered in the second version of the KFT.

Table 3: Consolidated functional and non-functional requirements

Requirement ID	Requirement Description	MOSCOW analysis priority
FR.01	The KFT offers a dashboard that can be opened from a variety of devices (Phone, Tablet, PC)	MUST
FR.05	The KFT needs to consider the technological requirements of the services and will take into account the specifics of the location details when proposing technology mixes.	MUST
FR.08	KFT needs to be able to provide insights on the economic (OPEX/CAPEX), socio-economical and environmental consequences of the proposed radio and edge connectivity mixes (indicators)	MUST
FR.19	The KFT needs to be able to process information at the farm, community and regional level, with correspondingly adjusted outputs	MUST
FR.25	The information stored in the KFT databases about radio, transport, and computation elements should always be updated with the latest information	MUST

FR.27	KFT needs to have documentation and pop-ups explaining all the steps and parameters a user needs to perform to run the tool	MUST
FR.37	The user should be able to indicate preference on technological, economical, environmental, social impact assessments (weights) to define prioritization of solutions suggested	MUST
FR.02	Users need to be able to specify a service and a series of needs for the service to be implemented. The needs are related to radio and computing characteristics	SHOULD
FR.03	Location details should be configurable: type of terrain, typical weather conditions, size of the farm in which a service is to be deployed	SHOULD
FR.04	The KFT suggests a mix of technologies to satisfy the requirements indicated by the users; if possible, at least 1 and ideally more.	SHOULD
FR.14	The KFT needs to visualize CAPEX/OPEX, quantity/number and type of infrastructure elements, specific technologies suggested, and other quantitative information about the suggested technology mix in a table or summary	SHOULD
FR.16	The list of suitable technological mixes proposed by the KFT for a service should orderable by specific categories, such as cost, energy consumption, etc.	SHOULD
FR.26	KFT needs to allow the user to ask questions/suggestions	SHOULD
FR.29	KFT should filter out potential requirement gathering questions that are not suited based on the inputs gathered from previous selections	SHOULD
FR.30	KFT should allow choosing different user profiles (e.g., farmer, researcher, public authority, etc)	SHOULD
FR.31	The tool needs to allow saving and loading sessions by creating / reading a file	SHOULD
FR.32	The tool needs to offer an expert and simplified mode	SHOULD
FR.38	The KFT shall expose relevant information about the technologies suggested.	SHOULD
FR.15	The info exposed in FR.14 needs to be presented in such a way that different solutions can be compared	COULD
NFR.01	The KFT should be usable by non-tech users	MUST
NFR.02	Easy and understandable visualization of results	MUST
NFR.08	Any information exposed or suggestions made by the KFT should be trustworthy	MUST
NFR.03	The results should be produced within a reasonable time	SHOULD

3.3 KFT Structure

The KFT architecture developed in T2.4 defined the main blocks and high-level functional modules that form the KFT and the relationships among them. It specified the main modules of the KFT that represent core functionalities, such as the user interface or the information processing tools, as well as high-level functional

blocks within those modules that break them down into specific features. The design also identified the interactions between those blocks and which information they produce or exchange. The main system components of the KFT fall into three main “layers”: the front-end, the back-end, and the databases, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: KFT structure and system components

The **front-end** is the graphical **HMI**, a user-friendly interface allowing the end-users to interact with the KFT, and is responsible to obtain the formatted data from the back-end and visualise them in a specific format/way e.g., graphical representation of the data. The design and implementation of the HMI are crucial elements in ensuring that non-expert personnel can easily engage with the tool. The HMI pages are mainly divided into (1) the “input” pages where the user can provide their requirements, i.e., the parameters that are required by the models in the back-end to process the user’s requirements and provide an output – these include sector and service selection,

area specification parameters such as weather and terrain, user equipment and service requirements such as the network latency and throughput which can be defined in a “Normal” view for a non-expert user, and an “Expert” view for a more experienced user, and the impact weights where the user can specify their preference in the impact aspect of the proposed solution; (2) the “output” pages, which provide the output of the back-end models to the user in an informative and user friendly manner – these include the proposed technology mixes, a techno-economic assessment, a socio-environmental assessment and a proposed business model.

The elements that constitute the **back-end** of the KFT are the **models** and **tools** that process the information that the user inputs to provide an output technology mix (connectivity and edge enabler) along with the relevant techno-economic, socio-environmental assessment and business models. The main purpose of the back-end is to connect to the databases through an Application Programming Interface (API) and obtain the required data. Once the data is obtained from the database, the format that the data must have to be pushed to the front-end is also edited by the back-end. The models working in the back-end are the following:

- **M1 – Technology mix finder model:** this model makes use of the ecosystem of connectivity technologies and edge processing enablers and their technical characteristic developed in T3.1 and T3.2, to propose suitable end-to-end solutions to the user, taking into consideration technological capabilities and limitations of these technologies that comply with the requirements provided by the user i.e., area specification and service requirements.
- **M2 – Dimensioning solver:** This model includes the dimensioning rules for the technological solutions based on users’ inputs. It provides dimensioning information of the proposed solution regarding deployment aspects of physical (infrastructure level) and overlay (service level) topology, placement and overall system dimensioning, including aspects of resilience and availability.
- **M3 – Techno-economic assessment model:** this model serves the purpose of estimating the cost of the proposed technology mixtures (last-mile connectivity and edge processing technological solutions). The primary focus is on assessing the economic aspects of these solutions at various levels, including farm, community, and regional levels. The model considers a range of factors to provide a comprehensive analysis such as: evaluation of the proposed last-mile solutions and dimensioning rules (capacity, coverage, and other technical parameters needed for the successful implementation of the solutions), and parameters related to the unit cost of network components, expected price evolution, and other relevant financial factors. The results of the techno-economic assessment are presented in the form of economic indicators such as Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) per system component of the proposed solution, and Operating Expenditure (OPEX) for various OPEX categories such as electricity, maintenance and installation, over a study period. It may later include more indicators such as Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), and payback period for the examined solutions.
- **M4 – Socio-environmental assessment:** this model is designed to evaluate the social and environmental impacts of the proposed solutions, considering a range of indicators to assess the broader implications of implementing these solutions at different levels, including farm, community, and regional levels. The key functions of the socio-environmental assessment model are a social exclusion analysis (considering indicators related to income, education, race, and age factors), a social innovation analysis (considering factors such as scale - number of people and networks involved, scope - institutional and policy setting, and resonance -abilities to change existing habits and imagine possibilities outside the scope of the present) presented as a social-life cycle assessment, and an environmental impact analysis, considering

environmental indicators such as electrical energy consumption of network components and devices, carbon dioxide emissions and biodiversity impact.

- **M5 – Impact weights assessment:** This model takes into consideration certain impact aspects of the proposed solutions (for example technological, economic, social and environmental impacts), and the preferred weights on these indicators that the user specifies in the final “input” page of the HMI, to produce a list of proposed solution ranked based on the user’s preferences.
- **M6 – Business model proposer:** this model plays a crucial role in the development and assessment of innovative business models designed to spark interest in rural areas, promote local initiatives on climate neutrality, empower people to act for change through environmental actions, and increase energy efficiency. The "Business model proposer" model follows a multi-actor, multi-value methodology, across 8 different sectors. The currently developed business models propose a business model canvas based on the selected user type: end-user (farmer, SME etc.), internet service provider (ISP), or public authority, and specific to the selected service, and provide information such as key partners, activities and resources involved, cost structure, value propositions and revenue streams.

The third “layer” of the KFT, the **databases**, contain all the information that the assessment models require in order to process the information and provide an output to the user. These might include tables on technical information of the connectivity and edge enabler technologies, the costs and energy consumptions of infrastructure elements and devices, area specification options such as topological and meteorological characteristics, the stock of business model canvases, and other information.

The KFT structure and system components are illustrated in Figure 1. It should be noted that this reflects the current version of the KFT, and there might be changes to the way the KFT is structured in the second version, D4.8.

3.4 Design Principles and Technologies Used

The following section outlines the implementation details of the KFT, including the design principles and technologies used.

3.4.1 KFT Front-end Design Principles

When designing an HMI, it is essential to adhere to the principles of GUI Design. A well-constructed HMI plays a crucial role in effectively communicating intricate data and insights to users in a visually engaging and user-friendly manner. GUI Design Principles offer a set of directives that guarantee the HMI's intuitiveness, efficiency, and ability to provide an outstanding user experience. By adhering to these principles, designers can develop an HMI that presents information clearly and in an organized manner, facilitating users in interpreting data and making well-informed decisions. Consistency in visual elements, including colours, typography, and icons, aids users in quickly grasping and navigating the HMI. Simplicity ensures that the HMI avoids unnecessary intricacies, allowing users to concentrate on the most pertinent information. Visibility ensures that vital data and essential metrics are prominently showcased, enabling users to easily locate and comprehend the insights they require. Feedback mechanisms, such as interactive charts or real-time updates, offer users a sense of control and confidence in their interactions with the HMI. Efficiency is attained by streamlining workflows and minimizing the steps needed to access and analyse data. Lastly, considerations for accessibility guarantee that the HMI is inclusive, permitting users of diverse abilities to access and benefit from the presented information. Through the

application of GUI Design Principles, designers can shape an HMI that amplifies data comprehension, empowers decision-making, and ultimately elevates the overall user experience.

The following main GUI design principles were considered for the design of the KFT HMI:

- **Aesthetically Pleasing:** Enhance visual appeal by adhering to presentation and graphic design principles, such as incorporating meaningful contrast between screen elements, creating clear groupings, aligning elements and groups, using three-dimensional representations when necessary, and effectively and simply utilizing colours and graphics.
- **Keep It Simple, Stupid (KISS):** Simplify interactions to ensure a seamless user experience. Minimize the effort required for users to engage with the UI. Use familiar concepts and metaphors to leverage users' prior experience and accommodate different user habits and abilities.
- **Clarity:** Ensure visual, conceptual, and linguistic clarity in the interface. Users should easily understand the information and functionality presented.
- **Comprehensibility:** Make the interface easily understood, friendly, and flow logically. Users should be able to follow the interface's structure and navigate through it without confusion.
- **Consistency:** Maintain a consistent look and operation throughout the interface. Elements should have a similar appearance and behaviour, actions should consistently yield the same result, and the function and position of standard elements should remain unchanged.
- **Control:** Allow users to maintain control during interactions and avoid interrupting them with errors. Users should have the ability to navigate and make decisions without unexpected disruptions.
- **Efficiency:** Minimize users' eye and hand movements by optimizing the interface. Ensure smooth transition between different control flows, keep navigation paths short, and prevent users from losing their work.
- **Simplicity:** Strive for an interface that is as simple as possible. Make common actions easy to perform, even if it means making uncommon actions slightly more challenging. Aim for uniformity and consistency throughout the interface.
- **Recovery:** Enable users to quickly return to a specific point if difficulties arise. Implement mechanisms to prevent users from losing their work due to errors or communication problems.

3.4.2 Cross Browser and multi device compatibility

Ensuring cross-browser and multi-device compatibility stands as a paramount consideration in contemporary web development. With the diverse array of browsers and devices available, it is imperative to guarantee that a website or web application operates accurately and uniformly across various platforms. This compatibility ensures a seamless user experience, irrespective of the browser or device in use.

The utilization of cutting-edge technologies such as HTML5, CSS3, and JavaScript plays a pivotal role in achieving cross-browser and multi-device compatibility, a strategy implemented in the development of the KFT. HTML5 furnishes a standardized markup language with enhanced support for multimedia, semantic elements, and responsive design. CSS3 provides advanced styling capabilities, encompassing media queries for responsive layouts and adaptable grid systems that cater to diverse screen sizes. JavaScript, as a versatile scripting language, enables dynamic functionality and interactive features that augment the user experience across a spectrum of devices.

Through the application of these technologies, developers can implement responsive web design techniques, ensuring that websites and applications dynamically adjust to varying screen sizes and orientations. CSS3's media queries empower developers to target specific device characteristics and apply corresponding styles. Furthermore, JavaScript frameworks and libraries simplify the creation of cross-browser and multi-device compatible applications by offering abstraction layers, browser feature detection, and polyfills to address inconsistencies across different browsers.

Dedicated testing and debugging tools tailored for cross-browser compatibility, such as browser developer consoles and online testing services, play a pivotal role in identifying and resolving any compatibility issues. In addition, adherence to web standards and the implementation of best practices in coding and design contribute to a smoother experience across browsers and devices.

In essence, achieving cross-browser and multi-device compatibility is indispensable for delivering a uniform user experience and expanding the reach of a website or web application. HTML5, CSS3, and JavaScript, complemented by robust testing practices and adherence to web standards, empower developers to craft resilient, adaptable, and accessible digital solutions that cater to diverse user environments.

3.4.3 Architecture

The illustration below (Figure 2) provides the architecture and main components of the KFT HMI, how the components communicate and how data flows between the various components.

Figure 2: Front-end basic architecture

3.4.4 Programming Languages and Technologies Used

The KFT and its interfaces were constructed using open-source standards and involve utilizing a mixture of programming languages and technologies, organized into client-side and server-side categories.

3.4.4.1 Front-end programming languages and technologies

Client-Side languages/technologies refer to the set of tools and languages responsible for executing code directly on the user's device, typically within a web browser. These languages, including HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, play a crucial role in shaping the presentation, interactivity, and overall user experience of a website

or web application. Upon a user's access to a web page, the client-side code is downloaded and executed on their device.

The primary objective of client-side languages is to craft an interactive and visually appealing interface for users. HTML defines the structural elements of the webpage, CSS manages visual styling, and JavaScript introduces interactivity and functionality to the page. Client-side code is primarily concerned with rendering the user interface, managing user interactions, and initiating asynchronous requests to the server for data retrieval. This approach ensures a dynamic and engaging user experience by processing tasks directly on the user's device rather than relying solely on server-side operations.

Here is a list of the client-side languages and technologies as referenced in the aforementioned architecture:

1. **HTML (Hypertext Markup Language):** HTML is the standard markup language used to structure and present content on the web. It provides a set of tags that define the elements and layout of a webpage. HTML is used for creating the structure and content of web pages, defining headings, paragraphs, links, images, tables, and other elements.
2. **CSS (Cascading Style Sheets):** CSS is a style sheet language used to describe the presentation and visual appearance of HTML documents. It defines the layout, colours, fonts, and other visual aspects of a webpage enhancing the look and feel of HTML elements, control their positioning and styling, and create responsive layouts.
3. **AJAX (Asynchronous JavaScript and XML):** AJAX is a set of web development techniques that enables asynchronous communication between the browser and the server without requiring a page reload. It uses JavaScript and XML (Extensible Markup Language) or JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) to exchange data with the server. This allows for dynamic updates on webpages, making them more interactive and responsive by fetching and displaying data without refreshing the entire page.
4. **jQuery Framework:** jQuery is a fast and concise JavaScript library that simplifies HTML document traversal, event handling, and animation. It provides a collection of reusable functions and utilities to streamline JavaScript development. jQuery simplifies common JavaScript tasks, such as manipulating HTML elements, handling events, making AJAX requests, and creating animations, resulting in more efficient and concise code.
5. **Additional 3rd party solutions for HMI purposes:**
 - a. **Zingchart Tool:** ZingChart is a versatile JavaScript charting library that empowers developers to build engaging and interactive data visualizations for web applications. With its extensive chart types, customizable options, and rich feature set, ZingChart enables developers to present complex data in visually compelling ways. It offers a wide range of customization options for styling, animation, tooltips, and interactivity, allowing developers to fine-tune every aspect of their charts. ZingChart supports real-time updates and integration with external data sources, making it suitable for dynamic and data-driven applications. With cross-browser compatibility and seamless integration with popular frameworks, ZingChart provides developers with the flexibility and ease of use to create stunning data visualizations.
 - b. **CanvasJS:** CanvasJS is a JavaScript charting library that simplifies the creation of dynamic and visually appealing charts for web applications. With a user-friendly API and comprehensive set of features, CanvasJS offers a wide range of chart types, customization options, and data handling capabilities. It supports responsive design, ensuring consistent chart rendering

across devices, and provides advanced features like drill-down functionality and real-time data updates. CanvasJS is compatible with all modern browsers and offers extensive documentation and support, making it a valuable tool for developers looking to create interactive and professional-looking charts.

3.4.4.2 Back-end programming languages and technologies

Server-Side languages/technologies pertain to the execution of code on the web server that hosts the website or application. These languages, including but not limited to Python, Java, PHP, or ASP.NET, are responsible for managing requests, handling data storage, and executing the underlying business logic. When a user engages with a webpage, their actions are transmitted to the server, where the requests are processed, and a response is generated to be sent back to the client.

The primary purpose of server-side languages is to manage data, perform calculations, interact with databases, and execute the essential logic of an application behind the scenes. Server-side code is instrumental in overseeing database operations and enforcing business rules, ensuring data integrity and security. It is responsible for generating dynamic content, such as personalized pages, and processing data submitted by users, contributing to the overall functionality and responsiveness of the application.

Here is a list of the server-side languages and technologies as referenced in the aforementioned architecture:

1. **ASP.NET Core:** Is an open-source, cross-platform framework for building modern web applications. It provides a unified development model and a set of tools for creating web APIs, Model-View-Controller (MVC) applications, and real-time applications. ASP.NET Core enables developers to build robust and scalable web applications with features like routing, middleware, authentication, and data access. It supports server-side rendering and handles the server-side logic of web applications.
2. **MySQL (database):** MySQL is an open-source relational database management system (RDBMS). It provides a scalable and efficient way to store, manage, and retrieve structured data. MySQL is used for creating, managing, and querying databases. It is commonly used in web development to store and retrieve data from server-side applications.

In summary, client-side technologies are primarily concerned with the user interface and interaction, executing on the user's device, while server-side technologies handle data processing, business logic, and database operations on the server. Together, they work in tandem to create dynamic and interactive web applications. The KFT was implemented using the aforementioned programming languages and technologies. However, the possibility of utilizing additional programming or development tools or languages remains open for consideration if it can demonstrate improved outcomes.

3.4.5 Deployment

The KFT is deployed on the cloud in the form of a Linux Docker. Docker, a widely embraced containerization platform, facilitates the packaging of applications and their dependencies into standardized and isolated units known as containers. These containers offer a uniform and transportable environment, ensuring seamless software execution across diverse computing environments.

Docker holds significance for various reasons. Firstly, it promotes consistency and reproducibility by encapsulating both the application and its dependencies within a single container. This guarantees consistent

software performance across distinct environments, including development, testing, and production. It mitigates the "it works on my machine" challenge, providing a dependable and self-contained package deployable anywhere.

Secondly, Docker promotes efficient resource utilization and scalability. Containers are lightweight, leveraging shared operating system resources. This allows multiple containers to operate concurrently on a single host machine without interference, facilitating the horizontal scaling of applications by deploying numerous containers to handle increased traffic or workload.

Furthermore, Docker streamlines the deployment process. Containers can be constructed, tested, and deployed as immutable units, minimizing the risk of configuration errors or incompatibilities. Docker also supports version control and rollback functionalities, enabling the straightforward management of different application versions.

In addition, Docker boasts support for an extensive ecosystem of pre-built images and containers available from public registries. These can be readily employed to deploy popular software components or services, expediting development and deployment cycles by eliminating the need to configure software from the ground up.

In summary, Docker provides a robust and adaptable platform for packaging, disseminating, and running applications. Its capabilities in ensuring consistency, portability, scalability, and simplifying deployment make it an indispensable tool in modern software development, including the implementation of the KFT.

3.5 Components Integration

Integration of the KFT in T4.4 refers to the process of bringing together and combining the various components, modules, or elements of the KFT into a cohesive and functional whole. This involves ensuring that different system components work seamlessly together and that the KFT operates as an integrated solution. The integration process involves configuring and connecting the different components of the KFT according to the predefined tool architecture outlined in T2.4. An iterative integration methodology is adopted, where the KFT system components are put together in a "loosely coupled way", implying that the components are designed to operate independently to some extent, allowing for flexibility, scalability, and interoperability.

The required inputs and outputs of each module, that govern the communication and flow of information between these modules, both between the front-end HMI and the back-end models, but also between the different models and the databases, were identified. The communication channels for each case were established, which include Application Programme Interfaces (APIs) for communication between the HMI and back-end models running on a different server than that of eBOS, or provision of algorithms, flowcharts and equations that describe the logic of each model or assessment tool, for the models that run on the KFT back-end hosted by eBOS. These communications are presented diagrammatically in the Unified Modelling Language (UML) diagram in Figure 3.

Figure 3: UML diagram showing communication channels between front-end and back-end (purple colour: models reside on external server & communication via API, orange colour: models reside on eBOS server – KFT back-end)

The back-end models showing in purple colour are not hosted on eBOS’ servers. M1 and M2 are hosted on ICCS’ server and M3 is hosted on INC’s server. The communication of those models with the front-end HMI (purple arrows) is established using APIs. The back-end modules shown in yellow colour run on the KFT back-end hosted by eBOS.

The sequence diagram presented in Figure 4 describes a typical session of a user using the KFT, demonstrating the flow of information and communication between the HMI and various models. The numbers in Figure 4, as well as in Figure 3, indicate the execution order of each step, as described below:

(1) By interacting with the KFT HMI, the user provides parameters related to the required sector and service, the level of assessment (local, community, regional) and user-type (end-user, ISP, public authority), location details (deployment area specification details – country, area size, terrain and weather information), service requirements (user equipment, intended use and expectations from the proposed solution), and the user weights that concern the impact categories. The output of the HMI is received by M1, M3, M4, M5 and M6.

(2) The M1-Technology Mixture finder model receives the inputted location details and service requirements from (1) and processes the information to generate a list of possible technology mix solutions that are feasible for the given set of inputs, however without taking into consideration any dimensioning rules. The output is fed into M2.

(3) The M2-Dimensioning solver model receives the output from (2) and processes the solutions to provide dimensions for the proposed list of technology mix solutions. The output of M2 is fed into M3, M4, and M5.

(4) & (5) The M3-Techno-economic assessment and M4-Socio-environmental assessment models receive the list of proposed technology mix solutions from M2, and for each technology mix they calculate techno-economic and socio-environmental indicators to generate an “impact score” for each solution. The impact scores are outputted to M5-Impact weights assessment.

(6) The M5-Impact weights assessment models receives the list of proposed solutions from M2, and their respective techno-economic and socio-environmental impact scores from M3 and M4. Furthermore, M5 receives the inputted desired impact weights that the user specified on the HMI (1). M5 considers the weights and impact factors to rank the solutions based on the preference of the user. The outputted ranked list of technology mix solutions is sent to the HMI.

(7) In this step, the user chooses their preferred technology mix from the ranked list of solutions, and this information is communicated to M3 and M4.

(8) M3 and M4 perform a detailed techno-economic and socio-environmental assessment for the chosen technology mix, and this is outputted to the HMI. In parallel, the M6-Business model proposer that has received sector, service and user-type information from (1) assesses the information to identify the most suitable business model for the given inputs. The techno-economic assessment, socio-environmental assessment, and business model canvas are outputted to the HMI for the user to view in the “outputs” pages.

Figure 4: KFT user's session – communication between modules

4 KFT Development

The KFT development phase constitutes the mock-up design stage, and the implementation stage. As described in Section 3.1, the collection of functional and non-functional requirements and architecture specification, led to the preparation of initial KFT mock-ups using the wireframing tool Figma. [1] These mock-ups were a living element that was shared to the XGain consortium and were constantly updated to reflect the latest design decisions taken by the consortium regards to the KFT main pages and their flow, and the KFT functionalities. Several iterations lead to the final KFT mock-up design, illustrated in Section 4.1.

In the KFT implementation stage, the final mock-up, functional requirements, and KFT architecture were utilized by the KFT developers team to implement the KFT as a web-based tool. It should be noted that the models defined in WP3 and WP4 are still being perfected and extended to provide more precise and useful outputs to the user. Therefore, certain features of the KFT are still under development, to be included in the second version of the tool. It should also be noted that the design choices for the KFT were made to maintain a degree of flexibility, to allow for easy modification of the databases and APIs, reshaping of visual content etc., once the models and tools from WP3 and WP4 are refined, and once the user feedback from WP5 is collected. The second version of the KFT (submitted as D4.8 in M35) will feature the finalised models and design choices based on the WP5 validation work. Further to that, in M27, at the end of the KFT testing phase, an “intermediate” KFT version will be developed, featuring the refined models and enhanced KFT functionalities, and aligning with project milestone 9, to be used in the KFT validation work (M27-M35).

4.1 Mock-up design

The KFT starts with a landing page, where the user can choose the language of the KFT, and acknowledge that data might be kept for evaluation and research purposes but it is fully anonymised (Figure 5). No user authentication is required, instead the user has the option at any time of their session to save and download a file with the input parameters they have provided, and load this file in a different occasion to resume their previous session. On the second page of the KFT, the user can view and navigate to the different main sections of the KFT.

Figure 5: KFT Landing page & Menu page

On the “Sector and Service selection” pages, the user can select the sector they wish to perform the analysis on from 8 different options (Figure 6). Once selected, the relevant services under that section will become available to choose from. This choice affects the assessment analyses performed at the back-end modules. The user then selects the “User type” which influences the proposition of business model. Lastly, the user chooses the desired “Level of assessment” for which the analysis should be performed, “local” referring to a farm-level assessment, while “community” and “regional” at larger scales.

Figure 6: Sector & service, user-type and level of assessment selection pages

On the location details page, seen in Figure 7, the user can specify details of the deployment area. These include the country and area size of the deployment location, terrain type and typical weather conditions. This information is the inputs parameters needed for the Technology mix finder model in order to identify the most suitable solutions based on the area specification, but also by the Techno-economic and Socio-environmental assessment models.

Figure 7: Deployment area specification page

In “Normal view” of the “Service requirements” pages (Figure 8) the user has to specify the type and number of devices they wish to employ in their area, the type of data that will be generated by those devices and any digital processing requirements for the data by the devices, and how fast the data should be processed. These inputs are required by the Technology mix finder and Dimensioning solver modules to assess and identify the most suitable solutions based on the technical requirements set by the user. In the “Normal view”, specification of the technical requirements is achieved through simple questions that a non-technically experienced user can understand and respond to.

Figure 8: Service requirements specification page – Normal view

The “Expert view” of the “Service requirements” page (Figure 9) is targeted to more experienced and technically-knowledgeable users that can quantitatively provide the desired data production rates and latency requirements for the solutions. The two “Normal” and “Expert” views ensure that the KFT HMI is relevant to users of a wide range of technical expertise, and can satisfy their demands both for a high-level as well as a more precise specification of service requirements.

Figure 9: Service requirements specification page – Expert view

In the last input page of the KFT, the user can set impact weights on certain impact categories that are going to influence the ranking of the proposed solutions (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Impact assessment weight specification page (conceptual design subject to modification)

In this first “outputs” page (Figure 11), the user is provided with the list of proposed technology mix solutions, ranked based on their impact weight preference. The list can be ranked also based on other criteria such as the cost, energy consumption etc. The user needs to select one of the solutions to proceed and view the results of the techno-economic and socio-environmental assessment of that solution, and the business model canvas, on the following page.

Figure 11: Propose technology mix solutions page

The output results pages of the KFT, as seen in Figure 12, begin with a summary page that illustrates a brief analysis from each assessment model: the techno-economic assessment model, the socio-environmental

assessment model, and the business model proposer. By clicking on each box, the user is navigated to the respective page showing more information for the specific assessment. The techno-economic assessment page provides information on CAPEX and OPEX for different components, and component categories for a chosen study period, and a pie chart to enhance visualisation of results. The socio-environmental assessment presents the carbon footprint and biodiversity footprint of the different infrastructure technological element and devices involved. A social Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for the chosen inputs is also presented in the form of a spider diagram. Lastly, the business model canvas in the Business Model page presents information for the chosen sector, service and user-type such as the key stakeholders involved, cost structure, revenue streams, value propositions etc.

Figure 12: Results pages (Summary & techno-economic assessment, socio-environmental assessment, business model canvas)

4.2 Implementation of KFT Version 1

Once the initial mock-ups were approved by the WP4 partners and the rest of the consortium, the KFT was developed and published (<https://xgain-kft.ebosrndportal.com/>). KFT development can be separated into two parts, the back-end and the front-end. The back-end is responsible to communicate with the database to obtain and format the data whilst the front-end is responsible to visualise the data, as described in Section 3.3.

For the KFT development, the overall architecture followed the established MVC paradigm. In this framework, the model component assumes the role of storing data and managing its associated logic. It serves as the repository for data transferred between controller components and other relevant business logic, manipulating and writing data to the database or employing it for rendering purposes. The model maintains communication with the view component and responds to directives from the controller, ensuring its timely updates. The view component takes charge of presenting the data, constituting the front-end of the system. Views are generated based on the data collected from the model, with a view requesting information from the model to retransmit the output presentation to the user. Additionally, the view visually represents data through charts, diagrams, and tables. Lastly, the controller component assumes the responsibility of managing user interaction. It interprets all user inputs, communicating with the model and the view to effect appropriate changes. The controller issues commands to the model to update its state and also directs associated views to modify their presentations. This dynamic interaction within the MVC architecture ensures a cohesive and responsive user experience within the Knowledge Facilitation Tool.

To demonstrate the capabilities and functionalities of the KFT, a session example is described below, with the input parameters provided by the user presented in Table 4, and the output results in Figure 13. It should be noted that the input parameters correspond to those that describe the UC 1 of the XGain project – “Rural Community Services, Spain”, and the outputted technology mix solution chosen is the actual solution that is being implemented in the UC.

Table 4: User Input parameters (Use Case 1) to KFT for session demonstration

Input field	Input information
Sector	Agriculture
Service	Drones Operation
User type / Level of Assessment	End-user; Community
Country	Spain
Area	0.0075 km ²
Terrain type	Valley
Weather	Sunny
Devices	Drones; 2
Service Requirements (Normal View)	Video streams; Image processing (e.g., object detection and recognition, image analysis) Yes, the data needs to be processed immediately (i.e., in real or near-real time)
Impact Assessment	Default 50% on all impact categories (model under development)

In this exemplary session that demonstrates a possible flow of pages, the user chooses “Agriculture” and “Drones Operation” as sector and service, therefore the technology mixture solution proposed will address the specific sector and application that corresponds to this selection. The user also selects a “Community level assessment”, and “Spain” as country, as such, a socio-economic analysis is performed to provide an adequate assessment for the drone-operations centre in the agricultural sector, in Spain. The user type is selected as “End-user”, affecting

the proposition of business model. A business model canvas is proposed for end-users i.e., farmers and their associations, SMEs etc., in the agricultural sector that plan to employ the use of drones in their operations. The type of devices, “Drones”, and their number, “2”, are considered in the economic and environmental assessment to provide CAPEX and OPEX information, and carbon and biodiversity footprints for the chosen type and number of end devices. Lastly, the definition of area, terrain type, and weather conditions that describe the deployment location, as well as the service requirements regarding the type of data, digital processing needs, and rate of processing, are significant in identifying the technologically feasible solutions for the user’s needs. The impact assessment weights provided are considered to rank the feasible solutions based on the user’s interest in those impact categories.

Results: Suggested Technology Mixes

Connectivity & Edge Enablers

↓	Access Connectivity	Processing Enablers	Internet Connectivity	Devices
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2 x 5G small cells (private)	1 x Near Edge Jetson (AGX) Xavier (5G Core + Service)	Fixed Access	2 Drones
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 X Wi-Fi AP	1 x Near Edge Jetson (AGX) Xavier (5G Core + Service)	Fixed Access	2 Drones
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 X 4G small cells (private)	3 x Extreme Edge Jetson Nano 2-GB Developer Kit, 1 x Near Edge Intel NUC 9 Pro(4G Core)	Fixed Access	2 Drones

Proceed

Summary Results

Selected

Agriculture Drones Operation

Connectivity & Edge Enablers

2 x 5G small cells (private) 1 x Near Edge Jetson (AGX) Xavier (5G Core + Service) Fixed Access 2 Drones

Techno-economic indicators

CAPEX Breakdown: Processing Enablers (50%), 5G Small Cells (private) (50%)

OPEX Breakdown: Electricity (30%), Processing Enablers (20%), 5G Small Cells (private) (20%), Maintenance (30%)

Socio-Environmental indicators

Carbon footprint analysis: 2 5G base stations, 2 Drones, 1 Near Edge Jetson Xavier

Social-LCA analysis: [Circular diagram showing various impact categories]

Business Model

Provide Feedback

Figure 13: Output results pages for Use Case 1 input parameters in KFT demonstration session

The first output page of the KFT “Suggested Technology Mixes” shows the most optimal suggestions for access connectivity and edge processing enablers, based on the user input parameters provided (UC 1 parameters), and ranked based on the user impact weights assigned on the impact categories. The user selects the preferred technology mix, the first option of the list in this example, and proceeds to view the results for the techno-economic and socio-environmental assessment and business model canvas of the chosen option.

The next page that appears is a summary of results, showing some figures of CAPEX and OPEX breakdown costs in the techno-economic indicators window, figures for the carbon footprint analysis and social-LCA study for the socio-environmental indicators window, and a preview of the business model canvas in the third window. The key user inputs (sector and service selection) and selected technology mix is also displayed for reference. The user can click on each of the three windows and navigate to a more detailed presentation of these output results.

In the techno-economic assessment page, the user can view the CAPEX and OPEX for each component and category for a study period of 10 years, and a detailed graphical representation of that information. In the socio-environmental assessment page, the user can see the carbon and biodiversity footprint of the different components and tools of the chosen technology-mix, with a graphical representation and description of this information. A social-LCA analysis is also presented graphically, showing the social categories impacted by the chosen solution with a reference scale to describe the impact. Lastly, in the business model page, the business model canvas that relates to the specific service and user type can be view.

Through the summary results page, the user has the option to “Provide Feedback” in textual form which will be sent to the KFT development team for optimisation of the KFT features. The user can also “Report a problem” by clicking on the relevant button at the bottom right of any page, to report other issues.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable is the first output of the T4.4 - Digitalisation and Integration of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool of the XGain project, and represents the initial version of the KFT, laying the foundation for a comprehensive tool that aligns with the project's core ambition of fostering sustainable, balanced, and inclusive development in rural, coastal, and urban areas. The KFT, designed to aid decision-making processes, offers a technology mixture proposition of access connectivity and edge processing solutions tailored to the distinctive needs of stakeholders such as municipalities, policymakers, and farmers.

In this deliverable, the design and implementation procedure of the KFT has been described and documented. The deliverable provides a detailed analysis of the implementation approach adopted towards the development of the KFT including task planning and design principles taking into account the purpose of the KFT within the XGain project.

Furthermore, the deliverable presents the roadmap from initial mock-up designs to the KFT development and implementation, showcasing the current features, functions, and capabilities embedded in the KFT. Additionally, it provides insights into the architecture of the KFT, elucidating how the front-end HMI communicates with back-end models through diverse communication channels, notably APIs. A thorough description of the front-end HMI structure and back-end models is provided. To demonstrate the functionalities of the tool, an exemplary session is presented using UC 1 parameters as inputs, and showcasing the resulting outputs.

This first version of the KFT will be taken as input in WP5 for validation purposes to ensure that the KFT performs seamlessly and effectively. The feedback collected from stakeholders in WP5 will be used to fine-tune the back-end models and front-end HMI, leading to the release of the second version of the tool, D4.8, in month 35 of the project. It should be noted that the models defined in WP3 and WP4 are still under development to provide more precise and useful outputs to the user. It is, thus, expected that certain elements like graph types and tailored visualization approaches, as well as specific features and functionalities of the KFT, remain subject to potential modifications based on the feedback to be collected from WP5 and further model developments.

References

[1] Figma. (2023, December 14). Figma: the collaborative interface design tool. Figma. <https://www.figma.com/>